

RESEARCH

Open Access

Impact of intelligent learning assistants on creativity of university students: a self-determination theory perspective

Harman Preet Singh^{1*} and Azira Ab Aziz¹

Abstract

In recent times, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been increasingly adopted in the educational domain. Intelligent learning assistants (ILAs) have emerged as a transformative AI tool enabling autonomous, personalized, and collaborative learning among students and enhancing their learning ability. However, prior research has not examined the impact of ILAs on enhancing student creativity. This research uses self-determination theory (SDT) as a theoretical lens to examine the impact of ILAs-enabled autonomy, competence, and relatedness on student creativity. The empirical analysis of 304 surveys of university students in Saudi Arabia indicates that ILAs-enabled autonomy, competence, and relatedness positively impact students' creativity. This study enriches the literature by informing the potential of ILAs-enabled autonomy, competence, and relatedness to enhance student creativity. The study contributes to the theory by extending applications of SDT in the AI-based educational domain. The study has important implications for higher education institutions to leverage AI tools (like ILAs) to enhance student creativity. Policymakers can utilize the study findings to promote an enabling environment for effectively utilizing AI tools (like ILAs) in the education sector to increase student creativity. Nonetheless, meticulous implementation of ILAs is essential to prevent inadvertent infringement on student autonomy, competence, or relational engagement.

Keywords Artificial intelligence, Higher education, Intelligent learning assistants, Self-determination theory, Student creativity, University students

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has recently experienced a surge in educational applications, transforming teaching and learning processes. It offers personalized learning, dynamic support, meaningful online interactions, and robust feedback capabilities [85]. It allows students to concentrate on valuable academic tasks and enhance their engagement and cognitive growth by automating responses to repetitive online queries [17]. These features allow students to assess their progress and learn effectively, which is essential for cultivating their creative skills [41]. A noteworthy instance of AI applications in

education includes Intelligent Learning Assistants (ILAs) that utilize adaptive technology and provide real-time help to enhance both individual and collaborative learning experiences.

The advancement of AI technologies has rendered creativity in digital learning essential. Creativity in digital learning can be defined as the ability to use information and communications technology (ICT) to develop new ideas, solutions, or behaviors [43]. AI in education can enhance students' creativity by facilitating exploration, manipulation, and engagement in challenging activities [16]. It also enables students to acquire skills in advanced concepts, generate unique ideas, solve complex problems, and produce transforming notions creatively [73]. Moreover, AI facilitates collaboration via virtual tools, enabling students to work in groups and develop

*Correspondence:

Harman Preet Singh

h.singh@uoh.edu.sa

¹ University of Ha'il, Ha'il, Saudi Arabia

© The Author(s) 2025. **Open Access** This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

innovative ideas. It enhances students' academic engagement via real-time one-on-one feedback, which enhances their creative abilities.

However, these advantages also raise concerns that certain students are becoming overly dependent on AI tools, potentially hindering their critical thinking and creativity if not properly regulated [85]. Excessive reliance on AI can inhibit students' critical thinking, which is essential for fostering creativity. AI tools can provoke apprehension regarding academic integrity, especially concerning content creation and plagiarism [6]. Deliberate integration and supervision of AI tools are necessary to ensure that AI supports educational objectives. Educational institutions should include adequate automation via AI while preserving opportunities for students to think independently and figure out solutions.

Since its inception in education, AI has endeavored to develop learning assistants to empower students to make educational decisions. ILAs are transformative AI tools that can facilitate student learning. ILAs like Blackboard, Microsoft Copilot, Google Translate, etc., influence students' learning. These tools are extensively utilized in Saudi Arabia, particularly among higher education students. Blackboard offers AI-integrated characteristics, including a plagiarism detection tool called SafeAssign, virtual classrooms, real-time chat, and group discussion forums, which promote collaborative and innovative learning [9]. Microsoft Copilot facilitates the generation of content, summarization of information, and brainstorming of ideas [5]. Google Translate assists native Arabic speakers in learning English by facilitating text translation [8].

ILAs can provide personalized learning to Saudi students, considering their unique needs and educational environment. For instance, Blackboard's SafeAssign promotes students' evaluation of their work's originality, cultivates critical thinking, and enhances creative expression [6], whereas Microsoft Copilot assists in generating ideas as students formulate innovative solutions [1]. ILAs consider students' learning patterns and learning ability to provide them with personalized learning content. ILAs can enable autonomous learning, engaging students to solve complex problems creatively. ILAs can also enable students to collaborate in a dynamic educational environment and develop creative solutions. For example, Blackboard online discussion groups encourage reflective peer-to-peer learning, cultivating collaborative innovation [6]. ILAs can also enhance the students' learning ability by allowing them to learn at their own pace. For instance, Google Translate facilitates the dismantling of language barriers among Saudi students, enhances their comprehension, and encourages active engagement with diverse learning resources [8]. Therefore, ILAs can

facilitate student creativity by fostering independent and collaborative learning while augmenting their learning ability.

To understand how ILAs foster student creativity, examining the motivational processes underpinning student learning is pertinent. We explore this using self-determination theory (SDT) as it can help to understand how motivating factors, enhanced by ILAs, can foster student creativity. SDT provides a theoretical lens to examine student learning ability, in which learners can engage in active and independent learning. It postulates three dimensions of learning: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Autonomy enables learners to make learning choices that fit their needs and develop their creative skills. Competence enables learners to enhance their learning capabilities and learn effectively, which enhances their creative abilities. Relatedness enables learners to develop academic relationships and learn collaboratively, which can influence their ability to develop creative solutions. Therefore, SDT can provide a suitable theoretical framework for examining student creativity.

Prior research has revealed that AI-enabled solutions can enhance student creativity [41, 49, 50]. Previous research has also revealed that SDT provides a pertinent theoretical framework for studying creativity [47, 48]. However, prior research has not examined the impact of ILAs on student creativity. Studies examining AI's impact on student creativity did not adequately explore the theoretical grounding by employing SDT. Most research examining AI-enabled student creativity has been conducted outside Saudi Arabia [49]. Saudi Arabia is an important context due to its substantial investments in modernizing its education sector and developing a knowledge-based economy under its Vision 2030 initiative [70, 76]. Moreover, given the increasing prevalence of ILA tools among Saudi university students, it is essential to investigate how ILAs, through the lens of SDT dimensions, can enhance student creativity in this unique context. Therefore, this research aims to bridge these apparent research gaps. This research seeks to contribute to the literature by empirically investigating the impact of ILAs-enabled autonomy, competence, and relatedness on the creativity of university students in Saudi Arabia. Accordingly, this research seeks to address the following research question:

RQ: Does ILAs-enabled autonomy, competence, and relatedness impact university students' creativity in Saudi Arabia?

The rest of the paper is ordered as follows: Section "Theoretical Framework" explains the theoretical framework related to SDT. Section "Review of Literature and Hypotheses Development" thoroughly reviews the literature on SDT dimensions (autonomy, competence,

and relatedness) and student creativity. Further, Section “[Review of Literature and Hypotheses Development](#)” also presents the theoretical model of the study. Sect. “[Research Methods](#)” delineates the research methods utilized in this study. Section “[Results and Findings](#)” is dedicated to presenting the results and findings of the study. Section “[Discussion](#)” discusses the current study results in light of the prior research. Section “[Conclusion and Implications](#)” presents the study’s conclusion and its theoretical and practical contributions. Finally, Section “[Limitations and Future Research](#)” highlights the study’s limitations and provides direction for future research.

Theoretical framework

Self-determination theory (SDT), formulated by Deci and Ryan [24], emphasizes human motivation. It posits that all persons have three basic psychological needs: autonomy (the sense of control and choice in one’s learning), competence (the perception of being capable of mastering academic tasks), and relatedness (the feeling of meaningful connection with peers), which influence their decision to act or refrain from action [21]. These three established self-determination theory constructs can provide a pertinent theoretical perspective on examining student creativity.

Autonomy and creativity

According to Deci and Ryan [25], autonomy refers to the intrinsic urge to self-organize experiences and behaviors in accordance with personal values. Chen et al. [19] suggested that autonomous motivation, including identified, integrated, and intrinsic regulation, contributes to creativity. Wang et al. [83] found a positive association between autonomy and creativity, indicating that students having decision-making freedom were more likely to generate creative ideas. Digital educational tools can enable students to learn at their own pace, improve student engagement in online education, and improve their creativity [70, 76]. Although digital tools offer adaptable learning environments that facilitate self-directed education, their advantages are not assured. Without intentional design, overdependence on automated learning may occasionally diminish students’ critical thinking [21]. Therefore, digital assistance solutions can meet the need for autonomy in online learning and enhance student creativity. However, this is contingent upon the extent of autonomy that digital tools afford the students in managing the learning process [83]. Accordingly, we can conclude that autonomy can serve as a basis for establishing creative expression among students. Consequently, it is essential that digital tools (like ILAs) are designed meticulously, ensuring a supportive framework

that simultaneously fosters student autonomy to enhance creativity.

Competence and creativity

According to Deci and Ryan [25], competence is a catalyst for human activity that must be fulfilled for sustained psychological well-being. People are considered competent if they possess the knowledge, skills, attributes, abilities, and behaviors to complete their tasks [79]. Jenó et al. [39] showed that students are more inclined to engage in academic activities voluntarily and consistently when they perceive themselves as competent, as this sense of efficacy enhances motivation and creativity. Xia et al. [86] reported that digital technology allows teachers to provide specific guidance to students for their learning activities, which enables student engagement. Álvarez-Huerta et al. [10] found a positive relationship between student engagement and their creative self-concept. Thus, educational technology can significantly enhance students’ competence and, subsequently, their creativity [4]. However, digital tools should be designed to challenge students rather than simplify tasks excessively. Excessively supportive tools may foster dependence, undermining learners’ sense of competence [75]. Thus, educational environments that foster students’ competence by providing suitable challenges, constructive criticism, and chances for skill improvement can influence their creativity. Therefore, digital tools (like ILAs) are most effective when they make learners competent to engage actively with knowledge, solve problems, and build confidence through effort.

Relatedness and creativity

Deci and Ryan [25] define relatedness as the aspiration to establish meaningful connections and relationships with people. Students’ perspective on relatedness suggests they are more inclined to participate in academic activities when they perceive support. Students feel supported if their educational environment respects and favors them. Students who feel relatedness are likelier to engage in their academic tasks, while those who feel disconnected are likelier to demonstrate less engagement or internalization [54]. Álvarez-Huerta et al. [10] and Guay [28] identified a favorable relationship between student engagement and their creative self-concept. Weng et al. [84] conducted research to examine the association between creativity and relatedness in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education. According to the study, fostering relatedness can influence students’ creative tendencies. However, while digital tools can facilitate contact and collaboration, particularly in online environments, they may also lead to feelings of isolation among participants if the interactions are

perceived as impersonal [10]. Thus, it can be inferred that a relationship exists between relatedness and creativity. To strengthen this relationship, digital tools (like ILAs) should be implemented to promote genuine academic connections rather than only enabling transactional communication.

SDT research applications

SDT has been widely applied in the education domain, like physical education [78], educational practice [54], online learning [18, 21, 30, 39], mobile learning [39] etc. Further, SDT has been utilized to study academic performance [54, 82], student engagement [21, 30, 54], academic motivation [18, 28, 39] etc. Standage et al. [78] reported on SDT's applicability to examining the physical education of school students. Vansteenkiste et al. [82] employed SDT to examine students' intrinsic motivation and academic performance. Niemiec and Ryan [54] used SDT in educational practice to explore student engagement, academic performance, and well-being. The research indicated that students exhibit enhanced learning and creativity when genuinely driven, especially in activities requiring conceptual comprehension. Chen and Jang [18] employed SDT to investigate learners' motivations in the online setting. Hartnett [30] utilized SDT to examine student motivation and engagement in an online learning environment. The study reported the applicability of SDT dimensions to promote effective learning in virtual classrooms. Jenó et al. [39] utilized SDT to study online and mobile learning. The study reported the applicability of SDT dimensions to examine students' motivations and learning outcomes. Chiu [21] employed SDT to examine student engagement in online learning amidst COVID-19. The study reported that educational technology with digital support improves student engagement in online education. Guay [28] applied SDT to study school students' academic motivation.

In view of the prior research and the wide applicability of SDT in the educational domain, this theory would provide a pertinent framework for examining this study.

Review of literature and hypotheses development ILAs-enabled autonomy and creativity

In recent times, AI has led to several practical applications in higher education. Noticeably, AI plays a prominent role in enhancing student learning [89]. AI tools (such as ILAs) provide one-to-one personal tutoring. According to a systematic review by Zawacki-Richter et al. [89], AI-driven education can encourage collaborative learning and promote online group interactions. Chiu [21] Hongkong study informed that AI tools can

promote adaptive and personalized learning, which is important for independent learning abilities [57]. Hamdan et al. [29] conducted a qualitative study in the USA and found that students who experience independent learning exhibit greater flexibility.

AI tools (such as ILAs) also provide systematic guidance for students. Broeck et al. [16] conducted a quantitative study in Belgium and found that autonomy can satisfy an individual if there is a dependency on a specific person or thing. Holmquist et al. [32] conducted a quantitative study in Sweden and reported that digital tools are helpful when students need to complete their work independently. Therefore, AI tools such as ILAs can be useful in enabling student autonomy in their learning.

Prior research has shown that student autonomy is vital for encouraging creative behavior. Peng et al. [60] Taiwanese quantitative research found that student autonomy allows them to decide their study needs. Jaquith [38] conceptual US study reported that the students who had complete autonomy in their coursework (for example, choice of media, learning procedures, etc.) exhibited greater creative tendencies. This point was further supported in the study of Hunter-Doniger [36] dual country (Germany and Netherlands) science, technology, engineering, arts, and math (STEAM) research. This research showed that autonomous learning among school students encourages creative play. Xie et al. [87] conducted a quantitative study in China, informing that technology-enabled autonomy is important for creative behavior. Thus, student learning autonomy encourages creativity.

Prior research has shown that AI tools (such as ILAs) are critical for encouraging adaptive and personalized learning [89] that encourages their learning autonomy [57]. Students' Learning autonomy is considered a predictor of technology-enabled creativity [36, 38, 87]. However, excessive reliance on AI systems may hinder students' learning autonomy. Structured individualized learning routes may restrict opportunities for exploration [85]. Furthermore, feedback or suggestions from AI tools (such as ILAs) may hinder learners' ability to make independent academic decisions [32]. These limitations emphasize the necessity to design ILAs that augment, rather than undermine, student-led inquiry.

Therefore, it is reasonable to expect that AI tools such as ILAs can encourage the creative behavior of university students when they support (not replace) autonomous learning. Thus, we hypothesize in the following manner:

H1 ILAs-enabled autonomy positively impacts university students' creativity.

ILAs-enabled competence and creativity

AI can play a prominent role in enhancing the students' competence (or self-efficacy). A Chinese quantitative study by Huang [35] indicated that students exposed to AI courses demonstrated greater engagement with the new technology, enhancing their competence. Li et al. [47] systematic literature review buttressed this point by informing that AI tools (like chatbots) assist learning and play a vital role in student engagement, which enhances their competency as they can apply knowledge in practical situations and create new knowledge. Furthermore, the systematic literature review by Tang et al. [81] emphasized that digital tools (such as digital games) increase students' intrinsic motivation to study, capture their interest, enhance academic participation, and increase their curiosity. Digital tools can also give students quick access to academic information, allowing them to relate to content from various viewpoints and apply new methods. The study also emphasized that these features enhance students' originality and competence. Therefore, AI applications (such as ILAs) can help students to develop essential learning competencies.

Puozzo and Audrin [63] conducted mixed methods (surveys and interviews) in Italy. The study informed that competence is required for students to achieve academic goals effectively. The study further informed that students would invest and persevere when completing academic tasks if they develop their competencies, leading to creative outcomes. This point was corroborated in Plotnikova and Strukov [62] experimental study conducted in Russia. The study indicated that students with a high level of competence demonstrated teamwork, critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and creative abilities. As per Yan et al. [88] quasi-experimental study conducted in Hong Kong, a high level of student competence encourages creativity. Xie et al. [87] conducted a quantitative study in China and found that technology-enabled competence is vital for creative behavior.

AI tools (such as ILAs) enable competence and can facilitate students engaging in creative behavior. For instance, Padhiyar and Modha [56] conceptual study informed that competence enabled by AI tools (such as ChatGPT) can support students' creativity. This is because utilizing AI tools (such as ChatGPT) assists in idea generation, content creation, and developing customized writings, which can unleash student creativity and stimulate thinking [52]. Further, Singh and Alshammari [74] conceptual study informed that a digitally enabled smart learning environment could develop Saudi students' competence and promote creative behavior. Therefore, technology-enabled competence is essential to students' creative behavior.

However, research suggests that excessive dependence on AI tools may reduce students' active engagement and intrinsic motivation, which are essential for cultivating genuine competence [85]. Overreliance on AI systems may reduce the necessity for problem-solving and decision-making since learners risk becoming passive consumers instead of active participants. AI tools may undermine academic integrity, as some students rely on system-generated information rather than autonomously acquiring knowledge [6]. Such concerns highlight the necessity for the judicious integration of ILAs, ensuring they augment rather than supplant genuine skill development.

Accordingly, we posit that AI tools like ILAs can inspire university students to act creatively when they support skill development, rather than aiding passive reliance. Thus, we form the second hypothesis as:

H2 ILAs-enabled competence positively impacts university students' creativity.

ILAs-enabled relatedness and creativity

AI tools enhance a sense of relatedness among the students as they receive prompt assistance and feedback. According to Molina et al. [53] quantitative research conducted in Ecuador, technology adoption in the classroom can enable students' to feel integration with the academic environment, increasing their learning motivation. Li et al. [47] conducted a systematic literature review and suggested that teachers could check, explain, support, and provide technical assessments while performing academic tasks with chatbots. Bernstein et al. [14] conducted a mixed-methods study in New Zealand and reported that AI tools (such as ChatGPT) enable students to enjoy academic exercises and better knowledge of the subject. Further, Holmquist et al. [32] Swedish quantitative study informed that digital tools increased the sense of relatedness of students with their academic environment and enhanced engagement.

According to Chiu [21] quantitative study conducted in Hong Kong, students' sense of relatedness can influence their behavioral, emotional, and agentic engagement, encouraging creative behavior. Daratul [22] conducted a quantitative study in Malaysia and reported that once individuals feel related to their work environment, work motivation is enhanced, and consequently, individual positive outcomes such as creative behavior are manifested. As per Ahmadi and Besançon [2] conceptual study, emotional effects (e.g., excitement and satisfaction), and teachers' attitudes toward students (e.g., concern and support) could influence creativity. For instance, students participate in course activities and have a

favorable attitude toward the course, which give them the confidence to tackle hard problems and motivate them to personalize their learning requirements. Singh and Alshammari [74] conceptual study informed that a personalized smart learning environment can develop Saudi student's creative behavior. Xie et al. [87] Chinese quantitative study suggested that technology-enabled relatedness is important for creative behavior. These studies indicate the potential for ILAs to offer chances for students to cultivate mutual emotional engagement with their learning environment.

However, some scholars have observed that AI tools (like ILAs) may provide a semblance of connection that lacks genuine feeling. Interactions with chatbots or other automated feedback systems, even if prompt, may not lead to genuine relational connections [85]. Excessive use of AI tools (like ILAs) may lead to less human engagement with peers and teachers and weaken the emotional and social basis of enduring creativity [32]. These considerations highlight the necessity of incorporating ILAs in a manner that enhances rather than supplants human interactions.

Since, previous research has indicated that AI tools are crucial for encouraging assistance and feedback in students' education, which fosters emotional and relatedness aspects [21, 53]. The AI-driven tools-enabled relatedness can encourage the creative behavior of students [22, 74]. Therefore, it is realistic to expect that AI tools (like ILAs)-enabled relatedness can foster university students' creativity when they support genuine academic interactions.

Thus, we hypothesize as follows:

H3 ILAs-enabled relatedness positively impacts university students' creativity.

Digital literacy and creativity

Digital literacy denotes students' knowledge, skills, and abilities to effectively utilize digital tools for their learning [58]. Kabakus et al. [40] explained that digital literacy is comprehensive when students can locate, access, organize, create, and synthesize digital resources, generate novel knowledge, produce media expressions, and communicate effectively in specific living contexts. This enables reflective analysis of the learning process and promotes constructive social action. As per Nikou et al. [55], individuals with a high level of digital literacy feel comfortable adapting to new technology. Although individuals may not be convinced of the technology's features and applicability, they understand that adaptability is a necessary skill set in the digital age. People with adaptability skills tend to have higher chances of creativity.

Therefore, Ramos et al. [64] suggested that people with adaptability skills tend to have higher chances of creativity.

As per Kormos and Suzuki [43], creativity is the ability to employ ICT to generate novel, previously unrecognized concepts and behaviors in unorthodox contexts or to tackle current issues through innovative approaches. Students will be considered creative if they can demonstrate finding learning resources and utilizing them as a reference to improve self-directing learning, either individual or collective [31, 33]. As per Herawan et al. [31], digitally literate students have a greater tendency to learn creatively. The study also concluded that the students who lack digital skills exhibit lower creative skills.

It is important to understand that varied levels of digital literacy influence students' efficacy in utilizing AI tools (such as ILAs) by enhancing their discovery of features, enabling them to assess online content, and permitting them to apply their knowledge creatively [33]. Students with greater digital literacy can engage more easily and creatively with AI tools. Conversely, inadequate digital literacy can restrict students' interaction with ILAs, undermining the tool's efficacy [31]. Incorporating digital literacy allows us to reduce this bias and improve the study model's ability to assess the impact of ILAs on student creativity. If digital literacy is not controlled, the study model risks merging its influence with the impact of ILAs on student creativity. Therefore, this research controls the effect of digital literacy to investigate the impact of ILAs on the creativity of university students.

Digital motivation and creativity

Digital motivation is the utilization of technology-assisted solutions to enhance or modify attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors regarding specific objectives and tasks, individually or collectively, through the application of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation [7]. Individuals who interact with digital tools (such as digital games) exhibit behavioral change, often enhanced by various digital motivation strategies. This is aligned with the findings of Pikhart et al. [61], which indicate that digital games as digital learning tool increases their intrinsic motivation [23, 44] and has a positive impact on creativity. Kormos and Suzuki [43] denoted that a creative individual is driven by intrinsic motivation. Lehmkuhl et al. [45] asserted that if individuals possess knowledge about creating games, they will be more curious to improve and become more creative [66].

Digital motivation influences a student's likelihood of utilizing AI tools (e.g., ILAs). Highly motivated students are more likely to utilize AI tools (e.g., ILAs) and sustain

their learning through cognitive engagement, thereby fostering a suitable atmosphere for creativity [61]. Conversely, a lack of digital motivation among students may lead to passive or ineffective use of technology, thereby limiting creativity [23]. These variations in digital motivation may lead to discrepancies in creativity. By accounting for digital motivation, we mitigate this bias and enhance the research model's capability to evaluate the effect of ILAs on student creativity. From a design perspective, the distinction is logical, as digital motivation includes both intrinsic (e.g., curiosity) and extrinsic (e.g., rewards) factors that influence creativity differently [7], hence, its incorporation can depict the genuine impact of ILAs on creativity. Consequently, we control the influence of digital motivation to assess the effect of ILAs on university students' creativity.

Based on the thorough review of the literature and theoretical framework of this study, we propose the following theoretical model in Fig. 1:

ILAs-driven autonomy, competence, and creativity are independent variables in this model. The university students' creativity is the dependent variable. The control variables are students' digital literacy and digital motivation.

Research methods

The present study utilized quantitative methodology to investigate the impact of ILAs on university students' creativity. This section delineates the study context, sampling and data collection methods, study variables, measuring instrument, empirical model, and data analysis method.

Study context

Saudi Arabia has prioritized digital transformation in higher education in accordance with Vision 2030. This policy has accelerated the incorporation of AI tools (such as ILAs) in Saudi universities. ILAs such as Blackboard, Microsoft Copilot, and Google Translate are prevalent in Saudi Arabia, particularly among higher education students. This study focuses on the University of Ha'il (UoH), a public university in Saudi Arabia, due to its integration of AI tools (like ILAs) within its educational framework.

The UoH has incorporated ILAs such as Blackboard and Microsoft Copilot into its educational system. UoH has established a robust IT infrastructure throughout its campuses to facilitate the use of these AI tools. All courses are immediately enrolled in Blackboard, enabling both instructors and students to access its comprehensive features, including online class tools, assignments, examinations, grading, and discussion forums. Blackboard has AI-integrated features, such as the plagiarism detection tool SafeAssign, virtual classrooms, real-time chat, and group discussion forums, which facilitate collaborative and creative learning [9]. Microsoft Copilot is integrated within the UoH's Microsoft 365 ecosystem. It facilitates interactive content creation, information summarizing, and idea generation for students and teachers [5]. Moreover, UoH students progressively use Google Translate to enhance their understanding of English academic material. Google Translate helps students remove language obstacles, improve comprehension, and engage with varied learning resources [8].

The UoH offers numerous training sessions for students and teachers to proficiently utilize AI tools (such as ILAs) proficiently, integrating online debates and

Fig. 1 Theoretical Model of ILAs impact on University students creativity

case studies as instructional strategies and interactive e-quizzes and e-forums as assessment techniques. These programs improve capacity by increasing teacher and student proficiency to utilize AI tools (like ILAs) for educational objectives and promoting a culture of digital participation.

Sampling method

For this research, we surveyed undergraduate students at the UoH in Saudi Arabia. We used non-probabilistic sampling to collect responses from students. The sampling activity engaged 575 students, of whom 304 completed the questionnaire, resulting in a response rate of 52.9%. This response rate is slightly higher than the 52.7% average observed in Baruch and Holtom's [13] evaluation of 490 survey studies that collected individual responses. A response rate of 50% to 60% is typically considered acceptable in educational research when supported by prompt reminders [13, 26].

Table 1 displays the study sample's characteristics.

Table 1 Study sample's characteristics

Variable	Sample (N=304)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Males	154	50.66
Females	150	49.34
Age		
18–25	249	81.91
26–34	46	15.13
35 and above	9	2.96
Level		
Year 1	82	26.97
Year 2	80	26.32
Year 3	72	23.68
Year 4	70	23.03
Total	304	100.00

Table 2 Variables of the Study

	Study variable(s)	Definition(s)	Source(s)
Independent variables	ILAs-enabled autonomy (IA)	Students' perceptions of using AI tools (like ILAs) to make their own decisions, create new ideas, and make their own choices	[36, 60, 89]
	ILAs-enabled competence (IC)	Students' perception of their skills or capabilities and confidence level while using AI tools (like ILAs)	[81]
	ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR)	The students' perception is to feel connected, be part of their learning environment, and build relationships using AI tools (like ILAs)	[21, 53, 87]
Control variables	Digital literacy (DL)	Students' knowledge, skills, and abilities to effectively utilize digital learning tools in their studies	[40, 43, 58]
	Digital motivation (DM)	The existence of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation when applying technology-assisted solutions in learning	[7, 45, 61]
Dependent variable	Creativity (CR)	The tendency of students to create new, unknown, and valuable ideas in unconventional situations or address existing problems in new ways	[41, 43]

Data collection method

The current study employed a structured questionnaire for data collection. The questionnaire covered all the constructs, as depicted in Fig. 1. The questionnaire was designed using a 5-point numeric Likert scale, with values spanning from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). Following protocol analysis [15, 27], the questionnaire was translated from English to Arabic to increase the respondents' comprehension. The questionnaire was prepared in Microsoft Office Forms and distributed online to increase the response rate and eliminate potential bias sources [71]. The survey's link was distributed via university email lists and student WhatsApp groups. With the permission of instructors, we visited classes to provide brief reminders to increase survey awareness and encourage student participation. These unobtrusive and straightforward reminders improved the survey response rate. Over 4 weeks, two data collection reminders were sent through the same channels. We ensured data integrity by mandating responses to all survey questions, thereby eliminating potential of missing values and invalid responses.

Variables of the study

Table 2 depicts the variables of this research. There are six variables, consisting of dependent, independent, and control variables. As Table 2 shows, university students' creativity is the dependent variable in the current research. The independent variables are autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The control variables utilized in the current research are digital literacy and motivation.

Measuring instrument

Table 3 depicts the measuring instrument employed in this study.

Table 3 Measuring instrument

Variable	Questions	Source
Independent variables		
ILAs-enabled Autonomy (IA)	Intelligent learning assistants provide me with valuable options and choices in my education Intelligent learning assistants provide me with interactive and virtual learning capabilities Intelligent learning assistants allow me to express ideas and opinions freely in my education Intelligent learning assistants allow me to make my own learning decisions	[16, 32, 87]
ILAs-enabled competence (IC)	I feel very capable and effective at using Intelligent learning assistants in my education I feel confident in my ability to use Intelligent learning assistants in my education It is easy to use the Intelligent learning assistants in my education I can complete difficult tasks in my education using Intelligent learning assistants	[16, 87]
ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR)	Intelligent learning assistants make me feel connected to my teachers and fellow students Intelligent learning assistants help me to establish or maintain satisfactory relationships with my teachers and fellow students Intelligent learning assistants make me feel a natural part of my class Intelligent learning assistants make me feel part of the university system	[16, 32]
Control variables		
Digital literacy	I possess knowledge of using different digital learning tools I possess technical skills for using digital learning tools I possess confidence in my ability to look for and evaluate information from the Web Digital learning tools enable me to effectively collaborate with my fellow students on educational projects and other academic activities	[55]
Digital motivation	I feel the need to try or experience new options in using digital learning tools I feel motivated when I use digital learning tools I feel an eager urge to use digital learning tools I feel that digital learning tools are meaningful for my education	[23, 44]
Dependent variable		
Creativity (CR)	Intelligent learning assistants help me solve my education problems creatively Intelligent learning assistants help me develop new and valuable ideas for my education I have received praise for sharing a valuable idea in my education using Intelligent learning assistants I can develop unique ideas using Intelligent learning assistants that other students have not tried	[33, 45, 66]

Empirical model

This study evaluates the subsequent regression model to ascertain the impact of ILAs-enabled autonomy, competence, and relatedness on the creativity of university students:

$$R_t = \beta^v + \beta^1 IA + \beta^2 IC + \beta^3 IR + \beta^4 DL + \beta^5 DM +$$

Where, CR = Creativity of university students. IA = ILAs-enabled autonomy of university students. IC = ILAs-enabled creativity of university students. IR = ILAs-enabled relatedness of university students. DL = Digital literacy of university students. DM = Digital motivation of university students. ε = Error term.

Data analysis method

The current study utilized ordinary least squares (OLS) regression as a statistical method to examine the various relationships as depicted in the theoretical model (Fig. 1).

OLS ensures a robust regression framework and methods for variance and covariance analysis and delivers results for numerous other tests. This method also helps to reduce the prediction error between the actual and predicted values [34]. This gives more insight into the structure of variables in the OLS analysis and highlights how individual variables play different roles in affecting output. This approach also corresponds to the purpose of this research.

Results and findings

Descriptive statistics

Table 4 portrays the descriptive statistics of the variables utilized in this research. The mean values of variables are: ILAs-enabled autonomy (IA) 4.11, ILAs-enabled competence (IC) 4.19, ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR) 4.05, digital literacy (DL) 4.08, digital motivation 4.13, and creativity (CR) 3.94. The coefficient of variation (CV) measures the extent of data variability in a sample compared

Table 4 Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variation
ILAs-enabled autonomy (IA)	4.11	1	5	0.77	0.19
ILAs-enabled competence (IC)	4.19	1	5	0.76	0.18
ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR)	4.05	1	5	0.86	0.21
Digital Literacy (DL)	4.08	1	5	0.81	0.20
Digital motivation (DM)	4.13	1	5	0.81	0.20
Creativity (CR)	3.94	1	5	0.91	0.23

Table 5 Constructs Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
ILAs-enabled autonomy (IA)	0.886
ILAs-enabled competence (IC)	0.887
ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR)	0.880
Digital literacy (DL)	0.900
Digital motivation (DM)	0.925
Creativity (CR)	0.919

to the population [69]. None of the variables employed in the current study possess a high CV (Table 4).

Reliability analysis

Table 5 displays the reliability analysis of the constructs. Cronbach’s alpha is utilized to assess the reliability of constructs. The Cronbach’s alpha values for the constructs are as follows: ILAs-enabled autonomy (IA) 0.886, ILAs-enabled competence (IC) 0.887, ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR) 0.880, digital literacy (DL) 0.900, digital motivation 0.925, and creativity (CR) 0.919. Previous studies indicate that Cronbach’s alpha values exceeding 0.9 are considered excellent, those ranging from 0.80 to 0.89 are deemed good, and those between 0.70 and 0.79 are regarded as acceptable [11, 80]. The Cronbach’s alpha values for the constructs in this research indicate that they are either good or excellent. Consequently, construct reliability is affirmed.

Correlation analysis

Table 6 depicts the correlation analysis among the variables of this research. A significant bilateral correlation may induce multicollinearity concerns in the regression model [20]. Coefficients will exhibit reduced accuracy, and p-values will fail to consistently indicate the importance of independent variables in the presence of multicollinearity among them [12].

Table 6 does not exhibit a strong relationship among the explanatory variables. The majority of correlations between explanatory variables are weak. A moderate correlation exists between the control variables of digital motivation and digital literacy; however, a strong correlation is absent (Table 6) [67].

OLS Diagnostic Tests

This study conducted diagnostic tests to confirm that the model conformed to the essential assumptions of ordinary least squares (OLS) regression analysis. At the outset, we examined the multicollinearity among the independent variables by computing their variance inflation factor (VIF), tolerance values, and condition index. No multicollinearity issues were detected since all VIF values were below the threshold of 5, tolerance values were above 0.1, and condition index values were below the threshold of 30 [42, 68, 72] (Table 7).

Table 8 presents the normality test outcomes on the residual study data using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov [90] and Shapiro–Wilk statistics [77]. The results indicate

Table 6 Correlation Analysis

Variable	IA	IC	IR	DL	DM	CR
ILAs-enabled autonomy (IA)	1					
ILAs-enabled competence (IC)	0.321	1				
ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR)	0.276	0.193	1			
Digital literacy (DL)	0.309	0.248	0.189	1		
Digital motivation (DM)	0.368	0.252	0.387	0.411	1	
Creativity (CR)	0.278	0.233	0.187	0.278	0.256	1

Table 7 Multicollinearity analysis

Variable	VIF-value	Tolerance	Condition Index
ILAs-enabled autonomy (IA)	2.875	0.189	4.424
ILAs-enabled competence (IC)	3.788	0.243	6.012
ILAs-enabled relatedness (IR)	3.015	0.194	8.432
Digital literacy (DL)	3.571	0.268	9.093
Digital motivation (DM)	2.353	0.214	9.815

Table 8 Normality tests

Test	Statistic	Sig. (p)
Kolmogorov–Smirnov	0.089	0.200
Shapiro–Wilk	0.975	0.342

p -values of 0.200 for Kolmogorov–Smirnov and 0.342 for Shapiro–Wilk, respectively. The p -values are greater than 0.05, signifying that we fail to reject the null hypothesis of study data residual normality (Table 8). Further, Fig. 2 shows the normal Q–Q plot of the standardized residual, which suggests a normal distribution [59]. Table 8 and Fig. 2 collectively demonstrate that the study data's residuals conform to a normal distribution.

We utilized the Breusch-Pagan and Koenker tests to assess the existence of heteroscedasticity in the data. The Breusch-Pagan and Koenker tests depicted p -values of 0.437 and 0.381, respectively (Table 9). This indicates the absence of heteroscedasticity among the variables, as demonstrated by the p -value for the Breusch-Pagan and Koenker tests being below 0.05 [3, 65].

OLS regression analysis

We conducted the OLS regression analysis to examine the relationship among the predictor and outcome variables. We confirmed the study model's fitness by analysis of variance (ANOVA) [51]. Table 10 depicts the ANOVA results. The F value of 142.014 is significant at a 1% significance level with 5 (regression) and 298 (residual) degrees of freedom. Thus, the ANOVA result shows the fitness of this study model.

Table 9 Heteroscedasticity tests

Test	Lagrange multiplier (LM)	Sig. (p)
Breusch-Pagan	0.676	0.437
Koenker	0.712	0.381

Fig. 2 Normal Q–Q plot of standardized residual

Table 10 ANOVA results

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	177.259	5	35.452	142.014	0.000
Residual	74.392	298	0.250		
Total	251.651	303			

Table 11 depicts the multiple regression results. The results demonstrate the study model’s good explanatory power, as indicated by the R² Adjusted value of 0.701 [37, 46]. This implies that the variables under investigation in the current research can explain 70.01% of the variation in university students’ creativity.

With the highest coefficient (0.465), the ILAs-enabled Autonomy (IA) variable shows a positive and statistically significant relationship with university students’ creativity. The result is statistically significant at the 1% significance level (Table 11). As a result, we accept the first hypothesis, H1.

With the third-highest coefficient (0.165), ILAs-enabled Competence (IC) demonstrates a positive and statistically significant relationship with university students’ creativity. The result is statistically significant at the 5% significance level (Table 11). Thus, we accept the second hypothesis, H2.

With the second-highest coefficient (0.336), ILAs-enabled Relatedness (IR) demonstrates a positive and statistically significant relationship with university students’ creativity. The result is statistically significant at the 1% significance level (Table 11). Thus, we accept the third hypothesis, H3.

Discussion

The research results supported the first hypothesis, which states that autonomy enabled by ILAs positively impacts university students’ creativity (T-stat = 6.458, p-value = 0.000). This result agrees with the prior research of Peng et al. [60], who indicated that autonomy could encourage students’ creative behavior. The current study also agrees with Jaquith [38], who asserted that students having autonomy in their coursework showed greater creative propensity. Further, the current study results align with Hunter-Doniger [36], whose STEAM research on school students highlighted the positive impact of autonomous learning on their creativity. Also, the study results align with Xie et al. [87], who stated that student autonomy encourages creative behavior. However, most prior research has informed the relevance of autonomy in promoting students’ creativity in a non-digital context. This research contributes to the literature by informing that digital AI tools (like ILAs)-enabled autonomy positively impact university students’ creativity. Nonetheless, an overdependence on AI tools (such as ILAs) may limit students’ opportunities for investigation [85] and the capacity to make autonomous academic decisions [32]. Therefore, incorporating ILAs that enhance, rather than hinder, student-led inquiry is imperative. This is important for Saudi Arabia as its educational framework under Vision 2030 encourages student learning autonomy due to the transition from traditional, teacher-centered instruction to modern, learner-centered methodologies [70]. The study findings suggest that AI tools (like ILAs) can foster student ownership of their learning and empower them through this educational shift in Saudi Arabia. Accordingly, Saudi universities should provide training and digital preparation to students to utilize AI tools (like ILAs) judiciously. Therefore, AI tools (like

Table 11 Multiple regression analysis

Variable	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	T-Stat	Sig. (p)
Constant	0.256	0.171	1.497	0.135
IA	0.465	0.072	6.458	0.000**
IC	0.165	0.081	2.037	0.027*
IR	0.336	0.067	5.015	0.000**
DL	0.101	0.068	1.485	0.139
DM	0.106	0.065	1.631	0.104
R-squared				Value
R ²				0.706
R ² adjusted				0.701

The 5% and 1% levels of statistical significance are denoted by the symbols * and **, respectively

ILAs) can facilitate student creativity in Saudi Arabia if carefully integrated to support student learning.

The current study results supported the second hypothesis, which posits that ILAs-enabled competence positively impacts university students' creativity ($T\text{-stat}=2.037$, $p\text{-value}=0.027$). This result aligns with Yan et al. [88] and Xie et al. [87], who stated that students' competence or self-efficacy helps encourage their creative behavior. The current study result agrees with Plotnikova and Strukov [62], who asserted that students with high self-efficacy or competence display higher creative skills. The current study buttresses the Padhiyar and Modha [56] results as they suggested that AI tools (such as ChatGPT) can help students' creativity. This study results also reinforce Singh and Alshammari [74] conceptual research, where they suggested that digital technology tools can promote the creative behavior of Saudi students. However, the majority of the prior research that examined the role of competence in promoting creativity has either been conducted in the non-digital context [62, 88], conceptual [74] or did not consider ILAs [56]. This research contributes to the literature by demonstrating that digital AI tools (like ILAs)-enabled competence positively impact university students' creativity. However, overdependence on AI tools (such as ILAs) may reduce students' active engagement and intrinsic motivation [85], undermining their problem-solving and decision-making skills and fostering passive learning [6]. Consequently, the prudent integration of ILAs into the educational system is essential to ensure they enhance (rather than replace) authentic skill development and creativity. This is of even greater significance in the Saudi context, particularly in view of the national emphasis on digital skills development under Vision 2030 [76]. Saudi educational institutions should promote a learning environment that requires students to apply their skills creatively. The study results also suggest the significance of a combination of methods that encourage student self-learning and the use of AI tools (such as ILAs) in Saudi Arabia, which is currently in the process of transitioning beyond traditional educational teaching.

This study supported the third hypothesis that ILAs-enabled relatedness positively impacts university students' creativity ($T\text{-stat}=5.015$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). This result reinforces the prior research of Chiu [21] and Xie et al. [87], who suggested that relatedness can influence students' creativity. This study's results reinforce Ahmadi and Besançon [2] research, which suggested that students who feel related to their educational environment exhibit greater individual creativity. The study results are also aligned with Daratul [22], who suggested that the psychological relatedness of the students encourages their creativity. The study results also align with Singh and

Alshammari [74] conceptual research, which informed that a personalized smart learning environment can lead to student creativity. However, most prior research has informed the relevance of relatedness in promoting students' creativity in a non-digital context. This research contributes to the literature by informing that digital AI tools (like ILAs)-enabled relatedness and positively impact university students' creativity. Nonetheless, AI tools (such as ILAs) enabled relatedness may not foster authentic relational connections [85] and may undermine the emotional and social foundations of lasting creativity [32]. Consequently, designing ILAs to augment rather than replace human interactions is imperative. This is particularly relevant in Saudi Arabia, where culturally rooted values of group learning and interpersonal connection are still prevalent [74]. Consequently, student-teacher connections and in-person cooperation in Saudi Arabia should be augmented using AI technologies (such as ILAs), rather than substituted. Saudi universities should create emotionally impactful learning experiences and enhance their e-learning infrastructures to foster creativity and cultural connectedness.

Further, the current study results are robust as we controlled the effect of variables like digital learning and digital motivation on the student's creativity. Prior research has not sufficiently employed such variables to examine students' creativity, especially in AI (such as ILAs). However, previous research indicates that students with superior digital literacy can creatively employ AI tools (like ILAs) [31]. Prior research has also demonstrated that digitally motivated students utilize AI tools (like ILAs) and maintain engagement in their learning [61]. By incorporating digital literacy and digital motivation as control variables, the study endeavors to depict the genuine impact of ILAs on the creativity of university students in Saudi Arabia. This method aligns with prior studies indicating that learners' digital literacy and motivation might influence students' learning results [31, 33, 61]. The inclusion of these control variables improves the study's validity and illustrates the effect of ILAs on the creativity of university students in Saudi Arabia.

Conclusion and implications

This study investigated the impact of ILAs on the creativity of university students. The study employed SDT as a theoretical framework to examine ILAs-enabled student creativity. SDT dimensions of autonomy, competence, and relatedness can influence student creativity. Still, prior research has not adequately applied these SDT dimensions empirically to examine ILAs-enabled student creativity, especially in Saudi Arabia. However, SDT can provide a suitable theoretical framework to examine student creativity as it has been applied in related

educational domains to examine academic performance [54, 82], student engagement [21, 30, 54], academic motivation [18, 28, 39] etc. Furthermore, SDT has been applied to study technology-enabled learning, such as online learning. Therefore, SDT dimensions of autonomy, competence, and relatedness have been selected as a theoretical framework to examine ILAs-enabled student creativity, thereby applying SDT within the context of AI-enhanced learning environments relevant to the ongoing educational changes in Saudi Arabia.

The present study employed quantitative methodology and developed a survey on a 5-point Likert scale to measure the impact of ILAs-enabled autonomy, competence, and relatedness on student creativity. Further, digital literacy and digital motivation were employed as control variables to ensure the robustness of the model. Further, the diagnostic tests such as correlation, multicollinearity, normality, and heteroscedasticity indicated the robustness of the study model and its conformity to OLS regression assumptions. The study model demonstrates a robust explanatory power of 70.1% ($R^2=0.701$), affirming the practical value of the study variables in the development of AI-based interventions aligned with Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 program.

Based on the analysis of survey responses from 304 University of Ha'il students, the OLS regression results informed that ILAs-enabled autonomy has a positive impact on the creativity of university students. This aligns with the prior research of Peng et al. [60], Jaquith [38], Hunter-Doniger [36], and Xie et al. [87], which suggested a relationship between autonomy and student creativity. However, this study goes further as prior research has not examined the role of AI tools (especially ILAs) enabled autonomy to enhance student creativity. This study enriches the literature by informing that AI tools (such as ILAs) enabled autonomy can enhance the creativity of university students. Further, there is a shortage of prior research in the context of Saudi Arabia that has examined the impact of AI tools-enabled autonomy on student creativity. This study empirically informs the positive impact of ILAs-enabled autonomy on student creativity in the Saudi Arabian context. However, overreliance on AI tools like ILAs may hinder university students' inquiry [85] and academic autonomy [32]. Thus, ILAs should be carefully incorporated to support student-led inquiry. This is crucial for Saudi Arabia because Vision 2030 fosters student learning autonomy by moving from teacher-centered to learner-centered learning methods [70]. AI tools (like ILAs) can empower Saudi university students through this educational change. Saudi institutions should effectively integrate AI tools (like ILAs) and train students to use them independently, especially in online or blended

learning environments where autonomy is necessary for enhancing educational quality.

Further, the OLS regression results reported that ILAs-enabled competence positively impacts university students' creativity. This is in accordance with the prior research of Yan et al. [88], Xie et al. [87], Plotnikova and Strukov [62], Padhiyar and Modha [56], and Singh and Alshammari [74], which informed a relationship between competence and student creativity. However, this study goes further as prior research has not examined the role of AI (especially ILAs) enabled competence to enhance student creativity. This study enriches the literature by informing that AI tools (such as ILAs) enabled competence can enhance the creativity of university students. Further, few studies have examined the impact of AI tools-enabled competence on student creativity in the Saudi Arabian context. Singh and Alshammari [74] have suggested that AI tools-enabled competence can enhance student creativity in Saudi Arabia, however, this was a conceptual study. This study empirically validates that ILAs-enabled competence positively impacts student creativity in the Saudi Arabian context. However, overusing AI tools like ILAs may decrease university students' active involvement [85], resulting in passive learning [6]. Thus, ILAs should be carefully integrated into the academic framework to foster creativity. This is especially important in Saudi Arabia, as Vision 2030 emphasizes digital skills development [76]. Saudi universities should encourage active self-learning and the use of AI tools (like ILAs) in classroom learning, ensuring these tools correspond with national objectives that foster innovation within a competency-based educational framework.

Lastly, the OLS regression results reported that ILAs-enabled relatedness positively impacts the creativity of university students. This is in accordance with the prior research of Chiu [21], Xie et al. [87], Ahmadi and Besançon [2], Daratul [22], and Singh and Alshammari [74], which suggested a relationship between relatedness and student creativity. However, this study goes further as prior research has not examined the role of AI (especially ILAs) enabled relatedness to enhance student creativity. This study enriches the literature by informing that AI tools (such as ILAs) enable relatedness and can enhance the creativity of university students. Further, prior research has not adequately examined the impact of AI tools-enabled relatedness on student creativity in the Saudi Arabian context. Singh and Alshammari [74] conceptual research informed that AI tools-enabled relatedness can enhance student creativity in Saudi Arabia. This study empirically informs that AI tools (like ILAs)-enabled relatedness positively impact Saudi Arabian students' creativity. Nonetheless, AI tools (like ILAs) may fail to foster genuine relational connections [85]

and could undermine the emotional and social foundations of enduring creativity among university students [32]. Consequently, ILAs should be carefully implemented to augment human connections rather than supplant them. This is essential since Saudi Arabia promotes group learning and engagement [74]. Saudi Arabia could embrace AI tools (like ILAs) to improve student–teacher connections and in-person interactions. Saudi universities should upgrade their e-learning infrastructures and deliver emotionally engaging learning to foster innovation and cultural connectedness, contextualizing ILAs as an extension rather than a replacement for relational learning in Saudi society.

In addition to contributing to the literature, this study contributes to theory by informing the potential of SDT as a guiding framework to enhance student creativity. Prior research has indicated that SDT can be a useful framework for promoting student academic abilities in technology-enabled learning, like online learning [18, 21, 30, 39], mobile learning [39], etc. This study extends the applications of SDT in the AI context, especially in ILAs. Further, prior research has utilized SDT to study academic performance [54, 82], engagement [21, 30, 54], and academic motivation [18, 28, 39] of students. The current research contributes to the literature by extending the SDT's application to student creativity, establishing its relevance to local educational values alongside global digital trends.

The study has some important implications for policymakers in the higher education sector. Policymakers can utilize the study findings to use AI tools to enhance student creativity. Specifically, policymakers can encourage higher education institutions to adopt AI tools (such as ILAs) to enhance student creativity. Higher education institutions can provide learners with an enabling environment that promotes AI tools (especially ILAs) based on autonomous, personalized, and collaborative learning. The academicians can embed AI tools (like ILAs) in their teaching strategies to enhance student creativity. Higher education institutions can also encourage administrators and teachers to adopt AI tools (e.g., ILAs) to promote student creativity. Further, higher education institutions can design training programs for administrators, teachers, and students to employ AI tools (e.g., ILAs) effectively. AI tools (like ILAs) must be explicitly developed and supported by clear guidelines, particularly in Saudi Arabia, where it is essential to balance tradition with technology to prevent undermining university student autonomy, competence, or relational engagement.

Lastly, this research has important implications for Saudi Arabia's higher education. Saudi Arabia's institutions have been investing substantial resources in modernizing their higher education sector following the

Saudi Vision 2030 government program. This study informs the potential of AI tools (such as ILAs) to increase the creativity of Saudi students. Therefore, Saudi Arabian higher education institutions can encourage stakeholders to implement AI tools (like ILAs) to enhance students' creativity. AI tools (like ILAs) should be strategically designed to enhance human instruction, especially in culturally collaborative educational environments like Saudi Arabia, which support the nation's vision for knowledge-based economic advancement and learner empowerment.

Limitations and future research

This current study has certain limitations that are typical in quantitative research. This study gathered data from only one public university in Saudi Arabia. Subsequent research may gather data from several Saudi universities. Future research can also collect data from private universities in Saudi Arabia and compare the differences in student creativity in public and private universities. Such evaluations of various universities can help generalize the research findings. This research gathered data from undergraduate students. Future research can also collect data from postgraduate students and compare the results between undergraduate and postgraduate students. Furthermore, future research can collect data from various gulf cooperation council (GCC) countries (e.g., Kuwait, Bahrain, United Arab Emirates, etc.) as they share a similar education environment to Saudi Arabia. The comparison of ILAs-enabled student creativity in various countries can reveal further insights into the mechanisms to promote student creativity. Further, such comparative research can enrich the current study findings. In this research, we employed quantitative methods. Future research can further enhance the findings by triangulating the quantitative results with qualitative methods. Future research can consider the current study limitations and further explore the potential contribution of AI-enabled technologies (like ILAs) on student creativity.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
CR	Creativity
CV	Coefficient of variation
DL	Digital literacy
DM	Digital motivation
GCC	Gulf cooperation council
IA	ILAs-enabled autonomy
IC	ILAs-enabled creativity
ICT	Information and communications technology
ILAs	Intelligent learning assistants
IR	ILAs-enabled relatedness
LM	Lagrange Multiplier
OLS	Ordinary least squares
SDT	Self-determination theory
STEAM	Science, technology, engineering, arts, and math

STEM Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
 US United States
 VIF Variance inflation factor

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Author contribution

The paper was conceptualized by HPS and AAA; methodology, software, data curation, and validation were conducted by HPS; HPS and AAA did data collection, investigation, and resource management; data analysis was performed by HPS; writing—original draft preparation was done by HPS and AAA; writing—review and editing was conducted by HPS and AAA; supervision was carried out by HPS and AAA; HPS and AAA conducted project administration. All authors have read and reviewed the manuscript. Acknowledgments Not applicable Funding Not applicable.

Funding

Not applicable.

Data availability

Data will be made available by the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declarations

Ethical approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

The survey respondents gave their informed consent to participate in the study. We informed the respondents about the purpose of the study and their rights. They were also assured that their personal information would be safeguarded during publication.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Received: 22 December 2024 Accepted: 30 April 2025

Published online: 27 May 2025

References

- Adetayo AJ, Aborisade MO, Sanni BA (2024) Microsoft copilot and anthropic claude AI in education and library service. *Library Hi Tech News*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/lhtn-01-2024-0002>
- Ahmadi N, Besançon M (2017) Creativity as a stepping stone towards developing other competencies in classrooms. *Educ Res Int* 1:1357456. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/1357456>
- Akwugberu HO, Umar SM, Musa UM, Ishaq OO, Ibrahim A, Osi AA, Ganiyat AF (2024) Breusch-Pagan test: a comprehensive evaluation of its performance in detecting heteroscedasticity across linear, exponential, quadratic, and square root structures using Monte Carlo simulations. *FUDMA J Sci* 8(6):233–239. <https://doi.org/10.33003/fjs-2024-0806-2826>
- Alhulail HN, Singh HP (2023) Impact of multimedia technology on university students learning agility and creativity. *Revista Amazonia Investiga* 12(70):189–199. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2023.70.10.17>
- Alhur A (2024) Redefining healthcare with artificial intelligence (AI): the contributions of ChatGPT, Gemini, and Co-Pilot. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.57795>
- Ali JKM (2017) Blackboard as a motivator for Saudi EFL students: a psycholinguistic study. *Int J Engl Linguist* 7(5):144. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v7n5p144>
- Ali R (2018) Digital motivation, digital addiction and responsibility requirements. In: 2018 1st international workshop on affective computing for requirements engineering (AffectRE), 27. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AffectRE.2018.00011>
- Almahasees Z, Meqdadi S, Albudairi Y (2021) Evaluation of google translate in rendering English COVID-19 texts into Arabic. *J Lang Linguist Stud* 17(4):2065–2080
- Almelhi AM (2021) The role of the blackboard LMS in EFL Course delivery during the COVID-19 Pandemic: investigating attitudes and perceptions of faculty and students. *Int J Engl. Linguist.* 11(2):46. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v11n2p46>
- Álvarez-Huerta P, Muela A, Larrea I (2021) Student engagement and creative confidence beliefs in higher education. *Think Skills Creat* 40:100821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2021.100821>
- Arof KZM, Ismail S, Saleh AL (2018) Contractor's performance appraisal system in the Malaysian construction industry: current practice, perception and understanding. *Int J Eng Technol* 7(3.9):46. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i3.9.15272>
- Arum KC, Ugwuowo FI, Oranye HE, Alakija TO, Ugah TE, Asogwa OC (2023) Combating outliers and multicollinearity in linear regression model using robust Kibria-Lukman mixed with principal component estimator, simulation and computation. *Sci Afr* 19:e01566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e01566>
- Baruch Y, Holtom BC (2008) Survey response rate levels and trends in organizational research. *Hum Relat* 61(8):1139–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726708094863>
- Bernstein S, Denny P, Leinonen J, Kan L, Hellas A, Littlefield M, Sarsa S, Macneil S (2024) "Like a Nesting Doll": Analyzing recursion analogies generated by CS students using large language models. 122–128. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3649217.3653533>
- Bielsa E, Cussel M, Raigal Aran J, Barranco O, Bestué C (2024) Recommendations on the translation of academic texts in the social sciences and the humanities. *Soc Sci Inf* 63(3):285–297. <https://doi.org/10.1177/05390184241261509>
- Van den Broeck A, Vansteenkiste M, De Witte H, Soenens B, Lens W (2010) Capturing autonomy, competence, and relatedness at work: construction and initial validation of the work-related basic need satisfaction scale. *J Occup Organ Psychol* 83(4):981–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317909X481382>
- Chan CKY (2023) A comprehensive AI policy education framework for university teaching and learning. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 20(1):38. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00408-3>
- Chen K-C, Jang S-J (2010) Motivation in online learning: testing a model of self-determination theory. *Comput Hum Behav* 26(4):741–752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.01.011>
- Chen S, Wang Q, Wang X, Huang L, Zhang D, Shi B (2022) Self-determination in physical exercise predicts creative personality of college students: the moderating role of positive affect. *Front Sports Active Liv* 4:926243. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspor.2022.926243>
- Cheng J, Sun J, Yao K, Xu M, Cao Y (2022) A variable selection method based on mutual information and variance inflation factor. *Spectrochim Acta Part A Mol Biomol Spectrosc* 268:120652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2021.120652>
- Chiu TKF (2022) Applying the self-determination theory (SDT) to explain student engagement in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *J Res Technol Educ* 54(sup1):S14–S30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2021.1891998>
- Daratul ACM (2017) The roles of work motivation and job involvement on the relationship between contextual factors and creative behavior. *Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia*
- De Grove F, Breuer J, Chen V, Ratan R, Quandt T, Van Looy J (2016) Validating the digital games motivation scale for comparative research between countries and sexes. In *ICA 2016: communicating with power*
- Deci EL, Ryan RM (1985) *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Plenum
- Deci EL, Ryan RM (2000) The "What" and "Why" of goal pursuits: human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychol Inq* 11(4):227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Fincham JE (2008) Response rates and responsiveness for surveys, standards, and the Journal. *Am J Pharm Educ* 72(2):43. <https://doi.org/10.5688/aj720243>
- Gjersing L, Caplehorn JR, Clausen T (2010) Cross-cultural adaptation of research instruments: language, setting, time and statistical considerations. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 10(1):13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-13>

28. Guay F (2022) Applying self-determination theory to education: regulation types, psychological needs, and autonomy supporting behaviors. *Can J Sch Psychol* 37(1):75–92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08295735211055355>
29. Hamdan A, Victoria L, William W, Watson SL (2020) Using personalized learning as an instructional approach to motivate learners in online higher education: learner self-determination and intrinsic motivation. *J Res Technol Educ* 52(3):322–352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2020.1728449>
30. Hartnett M (2016) The importance of motivation in online learning. In: Hartnett Maggie (ed) *Motivation in online education*. Springer Singapore, Singapore, pp 5–32. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-0700-2_2
31. Herawan E, Febianti YN, Safitri AL (2023) Digital literacy and student creativity through E-resources on the quality of learning in college. *J Educ Technol* 7(1):25–33. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jet.v7i1.43622>
32. Holmquist S, Inzunza M, Ghazinour M, Jonsson B (2024) Assessing autonomy, relatedness, and competence in higher education: the Swedish need satisfaction and frustration scale. *Educ Inq* 15(4):423–442. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20004508.2022.2116877>
33. Hong O, Park M-H, Song J (2022) The assessment of science classroom creativity: scale development. *Int J Sci Educ* 44(8):1356–1377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2022.2077466>
34. Xiaodan Hu (2024) Using ordinary least squares in higher education research: a primer. In: Perna LW (ed) *Higher education: handbook of theory and research: volume 39*. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, pp 649–725. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-38077-8_13
35. Huang X (2021) Aims for cultivating students' key competencies based on artificial intelligence education in China. *Educ Inf Technol* 26(5):5127–5147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10530-2>
36. Hunter-Doniger T (2021) Early childhood STEAM education: the joy of creativity, autonomy, and play. *Art Educ* 74(4):22–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00043125.2021.1905419>
37. Jafar R, Awad A, Hatem I, Jafar K, Awad E, Shahrour I (2023) Multiple linear regression and machine learning for predicting the drinking water quality index in Al-Seine lake. *Smart Cities* 6(5):2807–2827. <https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities6050126>
38. Jaquith DB (2011) When is creativity? Intrinsic motivation and autonomy in children's artmaking. *Art Educ* 64(1):14–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00043125.2011.11519106>
39. Jenő LM, Grytnes J-A, Vandvik V (2017) The effect of a mobile-application tool on biology students' motivation and achievement in species identification: a self-determination theory perspective. *Comput Educ* 107:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2016.12.011>
40. Kabakus AK, Bahçekapılı E, Ayaz A (2023) The effect of digital literacy on technology acceptance: an evaluation on administrative staff in higher education. *J Inf Sci*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515231160028>
41. Kavakoglu AA, Almacı B, Eser B, Alaçam S (2022) AI driven creativity in early design education - a pedagogical approach in the age of industry 5.0. In: *ECAADe 2022: co-creating the future - inclusion in and through design*, 133–142. <https://doi.org/10.52842/conf.ecaade.2022.1.133>
42. Kim JH (2019) Multicollinearity and misleading statistical results. *Korean J Anesthesiol* 72(6):558–569. <https://doi.org/10.4097/kja.19087>
43. Kormos J, Suzuki S (2024) Creativity and the linguistic features of argumentative and narrative written task performance. *System* 127:103531. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2024.103531>
44. Lafrenière M-A, Verner-Filion J, Vallerand R (2012) Development and validation of the gaming motivation scale (GAMS). *Person Individ Differ* 53:827–831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2012.06.013>
45. Lehmkuhl G, von Wangenheim C, Pacheco L, Borgatto A, Alves N (2021) SCORE – a model for the self-assessment of creativity skills in the context of computing education in K-12. *Inform Educ*. <https://doi.org/10.15388/infedu.2021.11>
46. Li Yi (2024) A study on the relationship between multiple regression analysis and students' achievement improvement in higher education english teaching. *Appl Math Nonlinear Sci*. <https://doi.org/10.2478/amns-2024-3004>
47. Li Y, Zhou X, Chiu TKF (2024) Systematics review on artificial intelligence chatbots and ChatGPT for language learning and research from self-determination theory (SDT): What are the roles of teachers? *Interact Learn Environ*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2024.2400090>
48. Lin CV, Shipton H, Teng W, Kitt A, Do H, Chadwick C (2022) Sparking creativity using extrinsic rewards: A self-determination theory perspective. *Hum Resour Manag* 61(6):723–735. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.22128>
49. Markauskaite L, Marrone R, Poquet O, Knight S, Martinez-Maldonado R, Howard S, Tondeur J, De Laat M, Shum SB, Gašević D, Siemens G (2022) Rethinking the entwinement between artificial intelligence and human learning: What capabilities do learners need for a world with AI? *Comput Educ Artif Intell* 3:100056. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2022.100056>
50. Marrone R, Taddeo V, Hill G (2022) Creativity and artificial intelligence—a student perspective. *J Intell* 10(3):65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence10030065>
51. Mercado Rueda AP (2023) Analysis of variance. *Translational Sports Medicine*. Elsevier, pp 157–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-91259-4.00099-0>
52. Modha S (2024) Impact of the usage of ChatGPT on creativity among postgraduate student. *Int J Sustain Soc Sci (IJSSS)* 9(1):40–45
53. Molina F, Molina M, Molina C (2022) Motivating learning through digital apps: the importance of relatedness satisfaction. *Int J Human-Comput Interact*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2022.2097777>
54. Niemiec CP, Ryan RM (2009) Autonomy, competence, and relatedness in the classroom: applying self-determination theory to educational practice. *Theory Res Educ* 7(2):133–144. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477878509104318>
55. Nikou S, De Reuver M, MahboobKanafi M (2022) Workplace literacy skills—how information and digital literacy affect adoption of digital technology. *J Documen* 78(7):371–391. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-12-2021-0241>
56. Padhiyar R, Modha S (2024) Impact of the usage of ChatGPT on creativity among postgraduate student. *Int J Sustain Soc Sci (IJSSS)* 2:83–92. <https://doi.org/10.59890/ijss.v2i1.1376>
57. Pan R, Qin Z, Zhang L, Lou L, Yu H, Yang J (2023) Exploring the impact of intelligent learning tools on students' independent learning abilities: a PLS-SEM analysis of grade 6 students in China. *Human Soc Sci Commun* 10(1):558. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02065-3>
58. Pangrazio L, Godhe A-L, Ledesma AGL (2020) What is digital literacy? A comparative review of publications across three language contexts. *E-Learn Digit Med* 17(6):442–459. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2042753020946291>
59. Pantoja-Pacheco YV, Yáñez-Mendiola J (2024) Method for the statistical analysis of the signals generated by an acquisition card for pulse measurement. *Mathematics* 12(6):923. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math12060923>
60. Peng S-L, Cherng B-L, Chen H-C, Lin Y-Y (2013) A model of contextual and personal motivations in creativity: How do the classroom goal structures influence creativity via self-determination motivations? *Think Skills Creat* 10:50–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2013.06.004>
61. Pikhart M, Al-Obaydi L, Klimova B (2024) Does digital learning stimulate creativity? *Cogent Arts Human* 11:2407103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2024.2407103>
62. Plotnikova NF, Strukov E (2019) Integration of teamwork and critical thinking skills in the process of teaching students. *Cypriot J Educ Sci* 14:1–10. <https://doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v14i1.4031>
63. Puozzo IC, Audrin C (2021) Improving self-efficacy and creative self-efficacy to foster creativity and learning in schools. *Think Skills Creat* 42:100966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2021.100966>
64. Ramos L, Sanchez S, Scyner L, Amigon R (2023) Teacher adaptability to change in special education: creativity and commitment to the institution. *Can J Educ Soc Stud*. <https://doi.org/10.53103/cjess.v3i2.131>
65. Romeo G, Buonaccorsi JP, Thoresen M (2024) Detecting and correcting for heteroscedasticity in the presence of measurement error. *Commun Stat Simul Comput* 53(11):5474–5490. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2023.2190061>
66. Runco MA, Plucker JA, Lim W (2001) Development and psychometric integrity of a measure of ideational behavior. *Creat Res J* 13(3–4):393–400. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15326934CRJ1334_16
67. Schober P, Boer C, Schwarte LA (2018) Correlation coefficients: appropriate use and interpretation. *Anesth Analg* 126(5):1763–1768. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000002864>
68. Shrestha N (2020) Detecting multicollinearity in regression analysis. *Am J Appl Math Stat* 8(2):39–42
69. Simón EJJ, GijónPuerta J, GalvánMalagón MC, Khaled Gijón M (2024) Influence of self-efficacy, anxiety and psychological well-being on

- academic engagement during university education. *Educ Sci* 14(12):1367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14121367>
70. Singh A, Singh HP, Alam F, Agrawal V (2022) Role of education, training, and E-learning in sustainable employment generation and social empowerment in Saudi Arabia. *Sustainability* 14(14):8822. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148822>
 71. Singh H, Alhulail H (2022) Predicting student-teachers dropout risk and early identification: a four-step logistic regression approach. *IEEE Access* 10:6470–6482. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3141992>
 72. Singh H, Alhulail HN (2023) Information technology governance and corporate boards' relationship with companies' performance and earnings management: a longitudinal approach. *Sustainability* 15(8):6492. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086492>
 73. Singh HP, Alodaynan AMM (2023) The role of educational technology in developing the cognitive and communicative skills of university students: a Saudi Arabian case. *Int J Adv Appl Sci* 10(7):157–164. <https://doi.org/10.21833/ijaas.2023.07.017>
 74. Singh HP, Alshammari K (2021) Impacts of digital technology-enabled personalized and adaptive learning on student learning performance: a TOE framework for Saudi Arabia. *Int Trans J Eng Manag Appl Sci Technol* 12:13
 75. Singh HP, Alwaqaa MAM (2023) The educational technology's impact on youth creativity and innovation: a case of Ha'il region of Saudi Arabia. *Revista Amazonia Investiga* 12(66):144–154. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2023.66.06.14>
 76. Singh HP, Singh A, Alam F, Agrawal V (2022) Impact of sustainable development goals on economic growth in Saudi Arabia: role of education and training. *Sustainability* 14(21):14119. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114119>
 77. de Souza RR, Toebe M, Mello AC, Bittencourt KC (2023) Sample size and Shapiro-Wilk test: an analysis for soybean grain yield. *Eur J Agron* 142:126666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2022.126666>
 78. Standage M, Duda JL, Ntoumanis N (2005) A test of self-determination theory in school physical education. *Br J Educ Psychol* 75(3):411–433. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709904X22359>
 79. Sulaiman T, Hamzah SN, Rahim SSA (2017) The relationship between readiness and teachers' competency towards creativity in teaching among trainee teachers. *Int J Soc Sci Hum* 7(8):10–13
 80. Taber KS (2017) The use of Cronbach's Alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education. *Res Sci Educ* 48(6):1273–1296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2>
 81. Tang C, Mao S, Naumann SE, Xing Z (2022) Improving student creativity through digital technology products: a literature review. *Think Skills Creat* 44:101032. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2022.101032>
 82. Vansteenkiste M, Simons J, Lens W, Soenens B, Matos L (2005) Examining the motivational impact of intrinsic versus extrinsic goal framing and autonomy-supportive versus internally controlling communication style on early adolescents' academic achievement. *Child Dev* 76(2):483–501. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2005.00858.x>
 83. Wang CKJ, Liu WC, Kee YH, Chian LK (2019) Competence, autonomy, and relatedness in the classroom: understanding students' motivational processes using the self-determination theory. *Heliyon* 5(7):e01983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01983>
 84. Weng X, Chiu TKF, Jong MSY (2022) Applying relatedness to explain learning outcomes of STEM maker activities. *Front Psychol* 12:800569. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.800569>
 85. Williamson B, Eynon R (2020) Historical threads, missing links, and future directions in AI in education. *Learn Med Technol* 45(3):223–235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2020.1798995>
 86. Xia Q, Chiu TKF, Lee M, Sanusi I, Dai Y, Chai C (2022) A self-determination theory (SDT) design approach for inclusive and diverse artificial intelligence (AI) education. *Comput Educ* 189:104582
 87. Xie Y, Zhou R, Chan AHS, Jin M, Qu M (2023) Motivation to interaction media: The impact of automation trust and self-determination theory on intention to use the new interaction technology in autonomous vehicles. *Front Psychol* 14:1078438. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1078438>
 88. Yan Z, Lee JC-K, Hui SKF, Lao H (2022) Enhancing students' self-efficacy in creativity and learning performance in the context of english learning: the use of self-assessment mind maps. *Front Psychol* 13:871781. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.871781>
 89. Zawacki-Richter O, Marín V, Bond M, Gouverneur F (2019) Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education -Where are the educators? *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 16:1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0>
 90. Zeimbekakis A, Schifano ED, Yan J (2024) On misuses of the kolmogorov-smirnov test for one-sample goodness-of-fit. *Am Stat* 78(4):481–487. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2024.2356095>

Publisher's Note

Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.